

WAYS TO ESTABLISH QUALIFICATION REQUIREMENTS FOR THE SUBJECT OF MUSIC CULTURE FOR PRIMARY SCHOOL GRADUATES IN GENERAL EDUCATION SCHOOLS AND WAYS OF FORMING IT

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Annotation

In this article, several new requirements and proposals are highlighted for the development of the teaching of music culture in schools and the development of students' learning, skills and interests.

Keywords

educational system, concept, music culture lessons, events, aesthetic culture, creativity, practical activity, musical knowledge, self-development.

Ministries and agencies, institutions, state and non-state enterprises and organizations, institutions of civil society, as well as citizens of the Republic of Uzbekistan form the system of implementation of the concept of the science of music culture. The concept implementation mechanism includes the following main measures:

to raise education, promotion and propaganda work to the level of the requirements of comprehensive reforms in our country;

to improve the professional skills and personal qualities of teachers in the field of music culture, to improve their pedagogical culture, and to make it the task of everyone to develop the qualities of artistic-aesthetic, spiritual and moral education and striving for physical perfection in students;

Regularly improving the educational process on the basis of effective pedagogical technologies and teaching methods tested in world experience;

To connect educational content with real life, interests and abilities of young people, to introduce advanced pedagogical technologies of education and training, to carry out systematic work on the development and stimulation of student abilities;

Creation of songs and cultural-educational animations, booklets that serve to increase the efficiency of work on creative activities;

holding republican and international conferences, forums and seminars by inviting the leading scientists of our country and foreign countries in order to eliminate problems in teaching this subject, to solve the issues of improving teaching;

conducting regular scientific-pedagogical monitoring of the educational process and effectively using IT technologies;

creating a series of didactic materials such as bright, colorful manuals, multimedia products decorated with various pictures for parents, pedagogues, children, young people;

It is required that the regulatory documents developed in the field of music culture be in accordance with the rules defined in this concept. Implementation of the concept is carried out in cooperation with international organizations, ministries and agencies, institutions, state and non-state enterprises and organizations, civil society institutions, and the public.

These concepts are first of all created for the formation of an educational system that is worthy of today's world standards of music culture and science, and secondly, the program is applicable for the teacher of science and for the development of his pedagogical skills. This concept is between the subject and the teacher, and now, in order to further develop and strengthen the students and their knowledge, skills and competencies, we set requirements for school students and graduates in the field of music culture. It also requires us to live. If we start with the primary grades, we will develop requirements for the subjects of music culture for primary grade students in the 1st-4th grade textbooks based on the "National Curriculum" mentioned above. This requirement must not exceed 3 competencies based on the National Curriculum and 4 activities in the course of the lesson.

1st class.

Aesthetic culture and creativity competence:

can write a violin (sol) key;

distinguishes musical sounds in nature;

can use notation to express sounds;

Self-development and self-care competence:

knows the name of seven sounds and sings them correctly in sequence;

sings various small songs;

sings songs suitable for psychophysiological characteristics;

Competence of development of practical activity:

distinguishes national instruments (circle, drum, trumpet, trumpet);

knows the location of seven notes on the note path and can write them down;

2nd class

Aesthetic culture and creativity competence:

distinguishes noisy and musical sounds;

distinguishes the type of performance (solo and accompaniment);

distinguishes the musician from the choir;

distinguishes a composer from a poet;

distinguishes musical instruments and song melodies from each other;

Self-development and self-care competence:

knows the rules of singing, follows them and sings expressively;

knows the series of sounds and sings them correctly up and down;

follows the rules of singing;

competence to develop practical activities;

distinguishes whole, half, quarter, half-quarter note forms;

3rd class

Aesthetic culture and creativity competence:

the ensemble can distinguish types;

distinguishes the means of expression of music;

distinguishes between major and minor;

Self-development and self-care competence:

correctly uses "reprise" signs when singing;

understands and performs songs;

Competence of development of practical activity:

knows the division of notes (whole note, half note, quarter note and semi-quarter note);

knows and applies 2/4 measurements;

knows the features of using the tact line; listens to music carefully;

4th grade

Aesthetic culture and creativity competence:

distinguishes clause and refrain from each other;

distinguishes between folk dances;

knows triad, tonic, alteration signs, tone and semitone and uses it in practice;

knows the names, functions and location of pauses and uses them in practice;

knows and uses 3/4, 4/4 measures;

Self-development and self-care competence:

Can sing folk sayings and songs correctly;

Competence of development of practical activity:

Uzbeks know folk instruments and distinguish them by timbre when listening to them;

sings learned songs;

Now, based on these requirements, among other basic subjects for the students of the elementary school and high school graduates, as well as the state exams at the end of the year, once for the graduates of the elementary school, as well as from practical subjects, i.e., the subject of music culture, I would propose a state exam for high school graduates. Exam requirements can be organized and compiled on the basis of the National curriculum and based on the 4 activities in the course of the lesson. It is appropriate to conduct both practical and theoretical lessons within the framework of songs, music literacy, and topics in music culture lessons from 1st to 4th grade. Through this, responsibility and interest in studying music will increase. The purpose of the subject is to form the spiritual, artistic, and moral culture of students, to listen to music, to develop the skills of a vocal choir, to teach musical literacy, to guide them to a profession, and to prepare listeners for professional music performance. Through these criteria and requirements, in the formation of psychological activities such as musical memory, attention, imagination, coordination of movements, in the development of artistic and musical taste, in listening and perceiving the works of Uzbek and world composers, in feeling the means of expression of the melody, knowledge of musical literacy (key word to know and apply in practice, to build skills by listening to tunes and songs, to distinguish genre aspects from each other, it helps a lot in the development of performance skills and skills.

At the end of the year for the graduates of the 4th grade, it is possible to include the subject of music culture in the state exam and develop the procedure for conducting it as follows. For example:

Exam Requirements:

1. Aesthetic culture and creativity competence:

a) Checking the level of distinguishing the sound of musical instruments;

b) Describing (creating) an event, a scene embodied in one's imagination after hearing the works of foreign composers given to listen to music in the classroom;

2. Self-development and self-care competence:

a) Dancing, performing rhythmic movements to the song while singing or performing movements to the tune of the dance;

b) to perform a 5-10-minute scene from a national fairy tale in groups of 4-5 students;

3. Development of practical activities:

- a) Write and perform a melody of at least 8 bars independently;
- b) Performing conducting actions to the played song knowing the number;

These requirements were based on the 3 competencies approved in the "National Program" of music culture, and the project provided the performance of 4 activities in the course of the primary school students.

It is planned to implement a number of activities in our National curriculum for the development of the scientific and methodical provision of the science of music culture. Among these requirements, the development of DTS in the science of music culture in harmony with advanced foreign experiences, international standards and national traditions, qualification requirements for graduates of general secondary education institutions in the science of music culture scientific and methodical requirements such as the development, the content of the science of music culture, its specific characteristics, the formation of an evaluation system based on the qualification requirements and the competences to be formed. The proposal that we are considering is considered a big step for the development of today's education system for primary school graduates, to improve their competence and use a system that meets the above requirements. It can serve as an important program to achieve the goal of the science of music culture in general education schools through pedagogical technology.

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